

DEDNAED

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 964248

Project Acronym: DeDNAed

Deliverable 1.2
Project Quality Plan

Due date of Deliverable: 31.08.2021

Actual submission date: 30.08.2021

Lead beneficiary for this Deliverable: BNN

Level of Dissemination: Public

Document History

Version	Date	Edited by	Comment
1	23.07.21	BNN	1 st draft
2	04.08.21	TUC	1 st review
3	10.08.21	BNN	revised version

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Abbreviations

AB	Advisory Board
CA	Consortium Agreement
DESCA	Development of a Simplified Consortium Agreement
DM	Dissemination Manager
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
GAS	General Assembly
IEM	Innovation and Exploitation Manager
IPRM	Intellectual Property Rights Manager
MST	Management Support Team
PC	Project Coordinator
PEDR	Plan of Exploitation and Dissemination of Results
PM	Project Manager
PMT	Project Management Team
PQP	Project Quality Plan
RM	Risk Manager
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

1 Introduction

The Project Quality Plan (PQP) as described in this document, defines the implementation of the general working mechanisms of the project on the basis of the definitions and regulations in the Grant Agreement (GA) and the Consortium Agreement (CA). The purpose of this document is to provide guidelines and principles, that ensure a high scientific and organisational quality of the DeDNAEd project throughout its lifetime. Furthermore, it defines a set of rules to organise day-to-day work, including procedures to be used, reporting mechanisms, the organisation of meetings, and the preparation of documents for submission to the European Commission (EC). Also, it contains a process description for reporting of project deliverables, including the procedures for internal review and the quality criteria, which will be applied in terms of quality assessment.

As the PQP reflects dynamic processes in relation with the project environment, it will partly refine during the course of the action. Any new version will be added to DeDNAEd's data repository platform with an email notice to all partners.

1.1 General project information

Project acronym: DeDNAEd

Project title: Cluster decorated recognition elements on DNA origami for enhanced raman spectroscopic detection methods

Grant agreement number: 964248

Starting date: 01.03.2021

Project Duration: 36 months

Call topic: FETOPEN-01-2018-2019-2020, FET-Open Challenging Current Thinking

Call: H2020-FETOPEN-2018-2019-2020-01

Type of action: RIA – Research and innovation action

Fixed EC keywords: Innate immunity and inflammation, Food biotechnology, Diagnostic biotechnologies (DNA chips and biosensing devices) in environmental management

Free keywords: lable-free, DNA origami, Biosensing, Atomic Cluster, SERS

Abstract: The project DeDNAEd is intended to develop a novel, innovative biosensing platform whose advantages and benefits are in terms of sensitivity, versatility and being ultrafast by an optical approach. Our platform will be based on the assembly and integration of sensing elements (transducer and bioreceptor) by DNA origami. The DNA origami will serve as a “nano bread board” in order to precisely control the position of these elements and thus the sensor architecture at the nanometer scale.

Metallic atomic clusters are integrated into a biological marker molecule (DNA or antibody) and thus represent the biological sensor element. This is specifically integrated into a nanoarray made of additional metallic nanoparticles precisely controlled by a DNA origami template and will lead to a significant increase in signal. DNA origami serves as an individually inter- and intramolecularly programmable nano bread board. A DNA origami consists of a single strand of DNA, folded by a thermal treatment and certain staple strands into any shapes (2D as well as 3D, dimensions between 10 and several 100 nanometers). So-called "sticky ends" on the surface of the DNA origami offer the possibility of an individual implementation of the sensing elements and nanoparticles, by means of correspondingly complementary oligonucleotides with a resolution of 2 nm. When the analyte is

connected to the sensor element, a change in the Raman signal can thus be detected without major delay using surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy. This sensor method is not bound to a specific biomarker molecule for the sensor element, but can be transferred to different marker molecules. This means a high degree of flexibility in the area of application, from medical technology to food monitoring. In addition, a transfer of the DNA origami-based sensor platform to flexible, textile substrates is carried out using lipid bi layers and the Langmuir-Blodgett method for later use as a wipe test or medical wearable.

1.2 Quality Objectives

The PQP sets out the quality assurance procedures for the project. The objective of this document is to assure a high quality for the deliverables, project outputs and results. In particular these elements have been developed on the basis of the specifications provided in the GA. It provides a baseline for monitoring the progress of scientific and administrative aspects. More precisely, the PQP depicts the following aspects:

- Coordinating the different project activities.
- Monitoring project progress and achievements, but also associated risk and contingency plans for the project.
- Monitoring the implementation of necessary changes within the work plan.
- Communication with the European Commission.
- Promoting the communication among the project beneficiaries.

1.3 Applicability

The present document is an internal guidance document from the start of project to the final acceptance of the final report. Any changes must be approved by the Project Management Team (PMT) and included in a revised version of the present document. In the event of a contradiction between the present document and any contractual document (such as GA or CA), the contractual document shall have precedence for all internal matters.

2 Project consortium

Table 1: List of the project beneficiaries.

Number	Name	Country	Short name
1	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET CHEMNITZ	Germany	TUC
2	ASOCIACION CENTRO DE INVESTIGACION COOPERATIVA EN BIOMATERIALES - CIC biomaGUNE	Spain	CIC biomaGUNE
3	KURT-SCHWABE-INSTITUT FUR MESS UND SENSORTECHNIK MEINSBERG EV	Germany	KSI Meinsberg
4	UNIVERSITE DU MANS	France	UM
5	UNIVERSITAET POTSDAM	Germany	UP
6	FUNDACION TECNALIA RESEARCH & INNOVATION	Spain	TEC
7	BIONANONET FORSCHUNGSGESELLSCHAFT MBH	Austria	BNN

Up-to-date contact details of each beneficiary can be found at the internal document repository platform, under: '1. Contact list'.

3 Management Structure

Reference documents: Grant Agreement, Consortium Agreement, Presentations and Minutes of Kick-off Meeting

Within this section, the management structure in DeDNAed should be described. An overview is given in Figure 1. Due to the small size of the consortium, the project management has a rather simple structure, which can therefore work both efficiently and transparently for all partners of the consortium and thus ensures a smooth running of the project. However, the objectives of DeDNAed require a strong and coherent management structure to support the progress of the project. It is structured as follows: the general assembly (GAS), the project coordinator (PC), the project management team (PMT), the management support team (MST), the project manager (PM), the dissemination manager (DM), the innovation and exploitation manager (IEM) and the IPR manager (IPRM) and the work package leaders (WPL). As an external supporter serves the advisory board (AB). The PC works in close cooperation with PM, DM and IEM as internal and external management and communication organ, which is monitored in its activities by the GAS, whereas the decision-making power lies within the GAS. The tasks and responsibilities of the individual functions within the DeDNAed management structure are described as follows:

Figure 1: Overview of the management structure within DeDNAed.

3.1 Project Coordinator

The PC acts as the intermediary between the parties and the funding authority (European Commission) and shall perform all tasks assigned to it as described in the GA and CA. The PC is responsible for:

- The correct execution of the whole research program.
- Proper communication among the partners and between the consortium and the EC.
- The global project management (planning, implementation and control of all project activities).
- The coordination of the overall project administrative and financial aspects.

- The preparation and submission of the project progress reports.

Project Coordinator: Danny Reuter (TUC)

3.2 Project Manager

The PM will be responsible, with all authorities, to run the project on a day-to-day basis. Moreover, the PM is responsible for document management within the project. The PM will also serve as Risk Manager (RM), see section 11 of this document

Assigned as Project Manager: Julia Hann (TUC)

3.3 Dissemination Manager

The DM will take care that the dissemination activities are executed according to what is defined in the Dissemination and Use Plan and will regularly monitor relevant international initiatives promoting the participation to those events where DeDNAed objectives and results should be presented and appropriately disseminated. The DM further authorizes the participation to any dissemination event.

Assigned as Dissemination Manager: Florian Walch (BNN)

3.4 Innovation and Exploitation Manager

The IEM coordinates and provides continuous support in efforts to:

- Identify all results with exploitation potential
- Define the best manner to manage intellectual property
- Find exploitation opportunities for DeDNAed solutions

The related activities performed in WP8 will be detailed and reported in the deliverable D8.2, including the Plan of Exploitation and Dissemination of results (PEDR).

Assigned as Innovation and Exploitation Manager: Goran Bijelic (TEC)

3.5 Project Management Team

The PM, DM and IEM will form, together with the PC, the PMT to support the PC for the efficient and successful coordination of DeDNAed using various tools (Project Quality Plan, Data Management Plan, PEDR). As part of the PMT, suggestions for filling positions or measures in the consortium are developed in order to present them to the GAS for decision making.

3.6 Management Support Team

DM and IEM will form the MST to support the PC for the efficient and successful coordination of DeDNAed using various tools (Project Quality Plan, Data Management Plan, PEDR). As part of the MST, suggestions for filling positions or measures in the consortium are developed in order to present them to the GAS for decision making.

3.7 General Assembly

The GA is composed of one authorized representative of each consortium partner institution. Decisions are taken by 2/3 majority and only if all members are present or represented (except those

cases detailed in the CA). Any GAS member may add circumstances to the GAS-agenda by written notification to all other members, at least seven days before the GAS. The responsibilities of the GAS include:

- Approving content, finances and intellectual property rights.
- Approving evolution of the consortium.
- Approving upon reviewing or amending the work-plan, the costs and time schedules.
- Approving upon press releases and joint publications with regard to the project.
- Approving appointment of experts to the positions of PM, DM and IEM.

The representatives of the respective consortium partner for the GAS are listed in Table 2.

Table 2: List of General Assembly representatives.

Name	Beneficiary
Danny Reuter	TUC
Aitziber López Cortajarena	CIC biomaGUNE
Michael Mertig	KSI Meinsberg
Marc Lamy De La Chapelle	UM
Frank Bier	UP
Nerea Iceta Briz	TEC
Christina Pfeifer	BNN

3.8 Work Package Leader

A WPL has been assigned for each work package (Table 3). The WPL is responsible for:

- Coordination of the work and the technical progress of the activities in the respective WP.
- Detailed planning, monitoring and reporting of each task in the respective WP, together with the other involved partners.
- Ensure the involved partners to commit the required resources to carry out their tasks in the WP.
- The technical coordination and preparation of the deliverables in the WP.

Each WPL will prepare a brief progress update to present at the GAS. The WPL reports monthly to the PM on the current status of the work carried out in the respective WP. Therefore, a prior telephone conference/ web meeting/ email conversation will be organized on a monthly base among the partners currently involved in the WP, for checking the status and to identify possible risks and deviations from the work plan as soon as possible. In case of a deviation or problem, the PC must be alerted and the GAS convened.

Table 3: List of Work Package Leaders.

Work Package	Name	Beneficiary
WP1	Julia Hann	TUC
WP2	Aitziber Cortajarena	CIC biomaGUNE
WP3	Michael Mertig	KSI Meinsberg
WP4	Marc Lamy de la Chapelle	UM
WP5	Julia Hann	TUC
WP6	Frank Bier	UP
WP7	Julia Hann	TUC
WP8	Christina Pfeifer	BNN

3.9 Advisory Board

The AB, consisting of three members, will be constituted by European stakeholders and provide advice to the consortium in matters related to technology development with a focus on exploitation. The AB will be set up in the first half of the project period, supported by the IEM. The GAS must agree to the selection.

The following profiles for the members of the AB would be beneficial for the project:

- Company with relation to human point of care diagnostics, especially infectious diseases
- Company with relation to cancer treatment/companion diagnostics
- Company with relation to food testing and plant testing

4 Time Management and Human Resource Management

Reference document: Grant Agreement

The management of the top-level scheduling and planning is within the responsibility of the PC. Regarding each work package, the WPLs are in charge of the internal scheduling and planning. The top-level planning is used to monitor the progress of the whole project. Each partner has been granted resources for each work package as specified in the GA. The summary of resource allocations per partners and per WP is presented in the GA (part A, page 28). The PC is responsible for controlling that all the resources are deployed according to the GA.

5 Decision Making and Conflict Resolution

Reference documents: Grant Agreement, Consortium Agreement

Decision-making and conflict resolution is defined in detail in the CA based on a Development of a Simplified Consortium Agreement (DESCA) model. The WPL will oversee the scientific/technical decisions regarding the specific tasks. The GAS oversees major decisions, risks and the implementation of the contingency plan (made unanimously with each participating organization having one vote). The GAS shall not deliberate and decide validly unless two-thirds (2/3) of its members are present or represented (quorum). If a member can show that its own work, time for performance, costs, liabilities, intellectual property rights or other legitimate interests would be severely affected by a decision of the GAS, the member may exercise a veto with respect to the corresponding decision or relevant part of the decision.

5.1 Voting Rules and Quorum

The General Assembly shall not deliberate and decide validly unless two-thirds (2/3) of its members are present or represented (quorum). If the quorum is not reached, the chairperson of the GAS shall convene another ordinary meeting within 15 calendar days. If in this meeting the quorum is not reached once more, the chairperson shall convene an extraordinary meeting which shall be entitled to decide, even if less than the quorum of members is present or represented. Each member present or represented in the meeting shall have one vote. A party, which the General Assembly has declared according to Section 4.2 of the CA to be a defaulting party, may not vote. Decisions shall be taken by a majority of two-thirds (2/3) of the votes cast.

5.2 Veto Rights

A member, which can show that its own work, time for performance, costs, liabilities, intellectual property rights or other legitimate interests would be severely affected by a decision of the General Assembly may exercise a veto with respect to the corresponding decision or relevant part of the decision. When the decision is foreseen on the original agenda, a member may veto such a decision during the meeting only. When a decision has been taken on a new item added to the agenda before or during the meeting, a member may veto such decision during the meeting and within 15 calendar days after the draft minutes of the meeting are sent. When a decision has been taken without a meeting, a member may veto such decision within 15 calendar days after written notification by the chairperson of the outcome of the vote. In case of exercise of veto, the members shall make every effort to resolve the matter which occasioned the veto to the general satisfaction of all members. A party may neither veto decisions relating to its identification to be in breach of its obligations, nor to its identification as a defaulting party. The defaulting party may not veto decisions relating to its participation and termination in the consortium or the consequences of them. A party requesting to leave the consortium may not veto decisions relating thereto.

6 Monitoring Structure

Reference documents: Grant Agreement, Consortium Agreement

6.1 Work packages

Within all WPs, a permanent monitoring shall assure proper execution of the project tasks. The following monitoring levels guarantee efficient and consistent control of project advancement:

- WP internal meetings on demand (responsible: WPL).
- Monthly WP meetings, usually web meetings (organisation: WPL, participation: WPL and relevant consortium partners).
- WP deliverables and milestones.
- Consortium meeting and GAs.
- Periodic reports / Final report.
- Monthly 4-column WP update

6.2 Deliverables

By the input from the responsible partner, the PMT is able to monitor the completion rate of deliverables. As a result, soon due dates and achieved stages can be monitored in an efficient and transparent way (see also chapter 7 Review Process for Deliverables).

6.3 Financial Monitoring

The PC is able to monitor costs and resources spent. As a result, the ratio of planned and actual costs and resources can be monitored in an efficient and transparent way.

6.4 Internal Reports

WPLs will provide activity reports on the progress of their respective WP to the consortium at the GAS (every six months). This reviewing of the project progress at intervals of six months is suitable to take decisions on possible work- and time plan adaptations and facilitates the compilation of the periodic reports and final report to the EC. The WPL reports include relevant managerial information and measurable progress made towards the deliverables and milestones in each task. Corresponding presentation templates will be adapted according to the PC's needs for monitoring the progress of work and will be available in DeDNAed's data repository template folder.

Moreover, WPLs will prepare a short overview of the activities and achieved targets within their respective WP ('Monthly 4-column WP Update') at the end of every month and send it by email to the PM. Templates are available within DeDNAed's data repository, in the 'Template' folder.

6.5 Monitoring and Reporting to the EC

According to the reporting periods as defined in the GA, a report demonstrating scientific work progress, and management and financial issues will be submitted to the EC. Therefore, all partners will submit a report to the PC strictly in accordance with the guidelines and rules provided by the EC. The PC will verify these reports and then submit them to the EC.

- Monitoring carried out by the European Commission: This external monitoring will be based on the review of reports and deliverables that are to be prepared and submitted by the PC on behalf of the consortium. Furthermore, upon request, review meetings will be organized.
- Periodic Activity and Management Report will be prepared as an overview of the activities carried out during the reporting period combined with a detailed justification of the costs incurred and the resources deployed by each contractor to justify their necessity.
- Periodic Report on the distribution of the Community's contribution to each contractor during that period and the final one at the end of the project.
- Publishable Final Activity Report, to summarize the project's activities over its full duration, covering project objectives, results and conclusions.
- Final Management Report consolidating the claimed costs of all contractors in an aggregate form covering the entire duration of the project, including the last reporting period.

6.6 Financial Reporting

The periodic financial report will include all requirements by the EC. The periodic financial report consists of:

- Individual financial statements for each beneficiary.
- Explanation of the use of resources and the information on subcontracting and in-kind contributions provided by third parties from each beneficiary for the reporting period concerned.
- A periodic summary financial statement including the request for interim payment.

7 Review Process for Deliverables

All deliverables prepared by the DeDNAed consortium, before being submitted to the EC, must undergo a project internal review. This review process applies to the deliverables defined in the project's description of work. Each deliverable is assigned a lead partner in the GA, this lead partner will be referred to as deliverable editor hereafter. The review process is organised in three main phases:

1. Work-package-internal review (after this, the deliverable should be ready for submission from the editor's point of view).
2. Reviewer's internal review.
3. Formal check and approval of the PMT.

These three phases are further organized in different tasks:

1. The PMT selects an internal deliverable reviewer (or asks one WP partner to assign one).
2. The editor sends the deliverable to the reviewer and the PMT, after having performed the WP internal review.
3. The reviewer sends his comments and proposals for changes to the editor and, if necessary, to the PMT.
4. The editor provides the reviewer and, if necessary, the PMT with the final deliverable version applying the reviewer's comments. Steps 3 and 4 may be repeated, if necessary.
5. The reviewer checks if all comments have been applied and sends an email approving the document to the editor and the PMT.
6. The PMT approves the deliverable by running a formal check.
7. The PC or PM uploads the deliverable via the EC Participant Portal. Moreover, the PM or PC uploads the document to DeDNAed's data repository platform.

For the successful execution of the procedure above, the following deadlines have been established, to be carried out after the WP internal review has been finalized, as depicted in Table 4.

Table 4: Deliverable review procedure within DeDNAed

Task	Responsibility	Deadline
Selecting the reviewers	PMT, or WPL on behalf of the PMT	Next GA (30th Sep 2021)
Sending the deliverable to the reviewer	Editor	21 days before due date
Sending comments and proposal for changes to the editor	Reviewer	14 days before due date
Providing the reviewer with the final deliverable version	Editor	7 days before due date

Approving the final deliverable version to the editor	Reviewer	4 days before due date
Approving the deliverable (formal check)	PMT	3 days before due date
Uploading the deliverable to the Participant Portal. Upload to DeDNAed’s data repository platform.	PC or PM	Submission date

7.1 Purposes of Review

The review of a DeDNAed deliverable is designed both to identify any important weaknesses in the document under review and to help to improve the document as much as possible. Written reviews should distinguish between bars to submission to the EC and other suggestions that, though they may substantially improve the document, do not compromise the validity of the findings and conclusions. This distinction will allow the project to avoid publication of unwarranted conclusions when it is not possible to incorporate all reviewer suggestions for improvements.

7.2 Role of Reviewers

The reviewer’s mandate is to make a reasoned judgment about the suitability of a draft document for submission, either “as it stands” or after particular recommended changes. Their judgments should consider the document’s objectivity, clarity, logic, focus, and general soundness – i.e. scientific and technical validity. Reviewers and editors do not always have to agree on issues, but reviewers may insist that alternative arguments are being discussed or at least acknowledged (e.g. in a minimalist approach, by adding footnotes stating: “*For contrary views, see ...*”, or “*As noted by a reviewer, ...*”) so that the opposite view can also be argued. Reviewers should think of themselves as advising the authors on the strengths and weaknesses of the deliverable so that they can determine what changes should be made before the document is submitted. Reviewers should also aim to communicate what types of changes would improve the document. Thus, they should do more than simply screen the document to assure that it meets minimum criteria – but they should suggest ways to improve it. Examples include suggestions for:

- A better organisation.
- More effective use of tables and figures.
- Additional conclusions that can be drawn from the analysis.
- Extensions of the analysis that could be easily incorporated into the deliverable.
- A presentation style more appropriate for the intended audience.

7.3 Review Criteria

The critical question for reviewers to answer is: “Are there any bars for submitting the document to the EC in its present form?” To be aware of such bars, the consideration of the following shortcomings should be included:

- clear statement of the document’s purpose and relationship to the project.

- adequate discussion of the connection between the conducted research and the problem(s) addressed.
- adequate review of the relevant literature.
- adequate documentation of facts.
- adequate description of data sources.
- appropriate application and adequate explanation of analytical methods.
- adequate specification of assumptions.
- proper interpretation of empirical data or statistical results.
- clear and logical development of conclusions.
- clear exposition.

Note: Within the review process, the editor and reviewer should use 'track change' and/or commentary functions and should take care of naming every new version accordingly (see chapter 10.2 Document Referencing).

8 Internal Communication Management

Reference documents: Grant Agreement, Consortium Agreement

8.1 Modes of Communication

For the overall success of DeDNAEd it is important that communication between all participants is transparent and open, so each participant is kept up-to-date on work progress, next steps, outcomes of meetings and task allocation. To ensure access to all official documents and relevant project information, DeDNAEd has implemented an easy-to-use, web-based and safe internal data repository platform. Along with the platform and meetings in-person, the DeDNAEd consortium will use the following communication channels: e-mails and phone calls for regular and daily communication and (video) conference calls in order to enhance team work between physical meetings. The aspect of virtual project communication will be given extra attention in the light of the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic and resulting travel restrictions.

Virtual meeting rules

At any virtual meeting, the establishment of the following rules should facilitate the implementation of comfortable and efficient meetings:

1. Before a telephone conference or virtual meeting:
 - a. An agenda with the points of discussion will be circulated in advance. This ensures an efficient use of time and serves as preparation for all participants.
 - b. Together with the agenda, the specific attendance method will be sent. This includes the number to be dialled, the code which might be asked for and/or the link to the web-conference platform.
 - c. Adjusting the background: Each participant shall find a meeting room where the amount of background noise is cut to a minimum. If there are more participants joining a room, side discussion should be avoided. If there is no other possibility, the microphone shall be muted meanwhile.
2. During the telephone conference or virtual meeting:
 - a. Do not speak out of turn.
 - b. Talk slowly and clearly.
 - c. Adhere to the agenda.
 - d. Introduce yourself before speaking.
 - e. Switch off or mute potential sources of noise, such as mobile phones.
 - f. Do not leave the conference call without discharge.

8.2 Meetings

The PC will organize regular meetings for the consortium and the WP leaders. If a meeting takes place at the premises of a partner, the PC will support the local organisation as far as possible (e.g. location of meeting places, rooms and equipment, preparation and distribution of materials). The PM will draft and communicate meeting agendas as well as the meeting minutes after the meeting has taken place. WP-internal meetings should be held on a monthly basis or on demand, organised by the respective WPL.

A proper organization is essential to guarantee a successful meeting. For all physical and remote meetings, a clear and well-structured agenda will be circulated at least one day before among the participants to allow for preparation. After each meeting, minutes will be distributed within the

project consortium. For every meeting a chairperson will be announced and is responsible for a productive meeting environment. Table 5 shows the frequency of the most important meetings of the individual parties.

Table 5: Planned frequency of the most important project-internal meetings.

Meeting	Frequency	Type of meeting
PC and PMT	Bi-monthly	In person or virtual
General Assembly	Every six months	Preferably in person, alternatively virtual
Work package	Monthly	In person or virtual
Advisory board	On demand	In person or virtual

Table 6 shows the anticipated timing of the General Assembly and Review Meetings, as well as their anticipated location (if known already). If possible, two will be in Germany and 3 in Europe.

Table 6: Planned General Assemblies and Review Meetings.

Meeting	Date	Location
Kick-off meeting	March 2021	Virtual
General Assembly	September 2021	Virtual
General Assembly	March 2022	?
Review Meeting 1	May 2022	?
General Assembly	September 2022	?
General Assembly	March 2023	?
General Assembly	September 2023	?
General Assembly	February 2024	?
Review Meeting 2	March 2024	?

Meeting Organization

Proper meeting organisation is essential to guarantee a successful meeting. For all physical meetings a clear and well-structured agenda will be circulated among the participants to allow for preparation. After each meeting, minutes will be distributed within the project consortium. The chairperson of the meeting will be responsible for a productive meeting environment. The PMT will make their best effort trying to combine GAS meetings with other events, such as conferences, and thus save costs and maximize the effect of travelling.

The GAS shall consist of one representative of each Party. Each Member shall be deemed to be duly authorized to deliberate, negotiate and decide on all matters. The PC shall chair all meetings of the GAS, unless decided otherwise by the GAS.

Representation in Meetings

Any Member:

- should be present or represented at any meeting.
- may appoint a substitute or a proxy to attend and vote at any meeting.
- shall participate in a cooperative manner in the meetings.

Convening Meetings

The chairperson shall convene ordinary meetings of the GAS at least once every six months and shall also convene extraordinary meetings at any time upon written request of any member.

Notice of a Meeting

The chairperson shall give notice in writing of a meeting to each member as soon as possible and no later than 14 calendar days preceding an ordinary meeting and seven calendar days preceding an extraordinary meeting.

Sending the Agenda

The chairperson shall prepare and send each member a written original agenda no later than 14 calendar days preceding the meeting, or seven calendar days before an extraordinary meeting.

Adding Agenda Items

Any agenda item requiring a decision by the members must be identified as such on the agenda. Any member may add an item to the original agenda by written notification to all of the other members no later than seven calendar days preceding the meeting.

Minutes of Meetings

The chairperson shall produce written minutes of each meeting which shall be the formal record of all decisions taken. He/she shall send draft minutes to all members within ten calendar days of the meeting. The minutes shall be considered as accepted if, within 15 calendar days from sending, no member has sent an objection in writing to the chairperson with respect to the accuracy of the draft of the minutes. The chairperson shall send the accepted minutes to all the members of the GAs, and to the PC, who shall safeguard them. The minutes shall also be uploaded by the chairperson to DeDNAed's data repository platform.

9 IPR Management

Reference documents: Grant Agreement, Consortium Agreement

The definition of pre-existing know-how, the establishment and protection of intellectual property rights (IPR) and ensuring confidentiality of shared information has been defined in the CA.

Briefly, the definition of ownership and transfer of foreground and access rights for implementation and use are described in general: Existing knowledge shall be the property of the partner who carried out the work leading to that knowledge. When several participants have jointly carried out work generating knowledge and their respective share of work cannot be ascertained, they shall have joint ownership of that knowledge. All scientific results originating in the project are intended to be freely disseminated, although participants may reserve the right to protect their technological contribution outside the consortium.

DeDNAed consortium is aware of the necessity to find a common strategy towards the management of the generated knowledge, in agreement with the commitment of the GA and in respect of each partner policy and objectives. The IPR management is settled in the CA taking into account both the partner's specific needs and the objectives and general rules of the EC.

10 Document Management

The PM is responsible for the document management in the whole project. Deliverable documents to the Commission as listed in the GA as well as all other reports, minutes, or presentations – shall be based on the document templates applicable for all documents to be created within the scope of this work. In addition, it shall be noted that all documents (internal and external) will be written in English.

10.1 Document Templates

A specific project identity for DeDNAEd has been developed, which will be used as a common public identity for all communication activities. EU funding will be acknowledged in all dissemination activities as follows:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 964248.”

Criteria for the visual identity of deliverables must meet the criteria of the DeDNAEd visual identity, including:

- Use of the DeDNAEd and EU logo.
- Acknowledgement of H2020 funding: “This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 964248.”
- Publication details.
- Fonts and headings as per DeDNAEd templates.

To facilitate to meet the DeDNAEd visual identity, templates for deliverables, presentations and monthly WP updates are provided and should be used by every partner for their creation. Templates for the DeDNAEd project are available for the consortium in the common data repository platform, and can be looked at in the annex of this Project Quality Plan.

10.2 Document Referencing

The setting of the document reference depends on the type of document. Each document is identified by a unique document identifier, stating the type of document, e.g. Deliverable, Milestone or Monthly WP Update.

The proper referencing of a documents is exemplarily examined for a deliverable, however also applicable to any other DeDNAEd document:

The file name of a deliverable shall include the project short name, the reference number, the title and the revision number when it is delivered to the EC. For internal circulation, the document name shall also include the term “draft”, the version number of the draft and partner name amending the document. Examples of the referencing of project documents are presented hereafter:

For internal circulation:

- DeDNAEd_Deliverable_X.X_Title_draft/final_vX_PartnerX
- DeDNAEd_Deliverable_1.2_Project Quality Plan_draft_v1_BNN

As the document has been through the verification and approval process, the final version is released:

- DeDNAEd_Deliverable_X.X_Title_r0_final

- DeDNAed_Deliverable_1.2_Project Quality Plan_r0_final

If a revision of the document is provided to the EC, then the revision number has to be incremented:

- DeDNAed_Deliverable_X.X_Title_rX_final
- DeDNAed_Deliverable_1.2_Project Quality Plan_r1_final

The last revision of each formal document shall be available in the assigned section of the document repository as a .doc file and/or .pdf file for the consortium and protected as .pdf regarding public deliverables.

10.3 Document Repository

The university-internal cloud of TUC is the designated repository for the DeDNAed project. The repository gathers all sorts of documents generated during the project lifetime. Within the repository, a folder structure has been implemented, which provides well-arranged access to all documents for the whole consortium.

10.4 Documentation Distribution

All internal and external reports, regardless of which issue or document type as well as source code, shall always be distributed by using the document repository platform. The direct dissemination of documents or source code via email is allowed.

11 Risk Management

Reference document: GA, Part B, p.18

DeDNAed will implement a Project Risk Management Process that will monitor and control the project risks in a continuous manner. The PM will perform the role of Risk Manager (RM) and oversee this continuous follow-up. Moreover, there will be a point dedicated to Risk Management in each GAS meeting.

Risk Identification: At the proposal preparation stage, the consortium has identified the main risks that the project will face. The RM will permanently observe the progress of the project with Risk Management Process.

Risk Response: Risk mitigation actions will reduce the chance that a risk will occur and besides will reduce the seriousness of a risk that may be realised.

Annex 1: DeDNAed Templates

Deliverable Template

Figure 2: DeDNAed Deliverable Template 1.

DELIVERABLE X.X

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Figure 3: DeDNAed Deliverable Template 2.

Figure 4: DeDNAed Deliverable Template 3.

Presentation Template

Figure 5: DeDNAed Presentation Template 1.

Figure 6: DeDNAed Presentation Template 2.

Figure 7: DeDNAed Presentation Template 3.

Figure 8: DeDNAed Presentation Template 4.

Monthly WP Update Template

PARTNER: A,B,C..

WPX, Status Report MX

Status

▶ Mastertextformat bearbeiten

Next steps

▶ Mastertextformat bearbeiten

Risks/Issues

▶ Mastertextformat bearbeiten

Deliverables/Dissemination

▶ Mastertextformat bearbeiten

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Figure 9: DeDNAed Monthly WP Update Template.